

AI-POWERED NAVIGATION FOR UNMANNED SURFACE VEHICLES

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Abstract. *This article presents the design and development of an AI-based obstacle detection and avoidance system for an Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV) participating in the Unmanned Surface Vehicle competition during TEKNOFEST Aerospace and Technology Festival 2025. The primary objective of the competition was to design a boat that could autonomously navigate from the start point to the finish line and return, avoiding all obstacles—particularly buoys—without external control. The system used combines visual detection (using a YOLO-based deep learning model) and distance sensing (through a LIDAR module). A dataset consisting of approximately 80–90% AI-generated images and 10–20% real photographs of buoys was used to train the object detection model. The model was trained to recognize three specific buoy types: horizontal orange, vertical orange, and yellow, which act as navigational boundaries and obstacles respectively. The integration of LIDAR and camera systems allows the vehicle to classify detected objects, estimate distances, and make navigation decisions autonomously. This work demonstrates how synthetic data and low-cost hardware can be combined to achieve robust obstacle detection while maintaining energy efficiency, making it suitable for future sustainable marine systems.*

Keywords: *Autonomous Surface Vehicle, Obstacle Detection, Deep Learning, YOLO, LIDAR, Synthetic Dataset.*

1. Introduction

Advancements in the field of AI and autonomous technology over the last decade allowed creation of autonomous, intelligent marine systems, which are capable of navigating without minimal human intervention. It has also made the creation of such systems easier.

An opportunity to design such a system became available to us during TEKNOFEST Aerospace and Technology Festival 2025, which included an Unmanned Surface Vehicle competition. Participating teams were required to design an autonomous boat capable of navigating a track with borders marked by buoys. The boat must complete the track without any human input, and avoid randomly placed obstacles along the way. Horizontal and vertical orange buoys

served as the left and right borders of the track, respectively, while yellow buoys represented obstacles positioned between them. The system was expected to recognize these buoys, interpret their meaning, and act accordingly.

The challenge is to create an obstacle detection and classification system that would operate in real time, under various lighting and water conditions. To create a system that meets the goals, a dual perception system was implemented—combining a LIDAR sensor for spatial awareness combined with a camera using a YOLO-based deep learning model for object detection and classification. This integration allowed the vehicle to understand its surroundings efficiently in order to avoid the obstacles, and generally navigate with higher accuracy.

2. Methodology

The overall system architecture consists of three major components: a LIDAR-based distance detection module, a camera module feeding data to the YOLO model, and a central controlling algorithm that uses the data from both sensors as input to determine navigation action as output.

2.1 Dataset Preparation

One of the problems encountered during the work on this task was the absence of a suitable dataset. (If such a dataset existed, it was not available to us, nor were we aware about it.) To train a model on a dataset, a diverse dataset representing the three buoy classes had to be created first. Additionally, taking photos of the buoys to form a dataset was impossible.

At first, some images and stock photos freely available on the Internet were gathered. However, very few images were similar enough to what the task required. To address this, it was proposed to generate such images synthetically using large and more powerful freely available AI tools, including tools offered by OpenAI and Google. These tools were made to produce images with variations in lighting, reflections, wave intensity, and backgrounds. A smaller portion of available actual buoy photographs was added to the dataset as well. The final dataset composition contained approximately 80–90% AI-generated data and 10–20% realworld images.

It was decided that from all available options, Roboflow offered the most convenient platform for our purposes. The images were evenly distributed between the team members, each labeling their own images. Since YOLO uses the bounding box approach, this was also the approach we used for labeling.

2.2 Model Training

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection algorithm was selected for its high-speed performance and suitability for embedded systems. YOLO has a long history of development and optimization, and provides a wide choice of models. In particular, YOLO v11 N was selected, v11 being the latest available model pack and N being the most lightweight among them. The model was trained on the custom buoy dataset for three output classes: *HorOr* (Orange - Horizontal), *VerOr* (Orange - Vertical), and *Yellow*. Training was conducted using the environment provided by Roboflow.

2.3 Sensor Fusion and System Design

A LIDAR sensor was mounted on the top of the boat to provide continuous distance measurements in a 360-degree radius. The sensor operates by emitting laser pulses and measuring their return time, thus identifying the position and proximity of nearby objects. The camera, located just below the LIDAR, captures live video frames which are then processed by the YOLO detection model in real time.

The sensor fusion process works as follows:

1. The LIDAR continuously monitors the environment and flags any (potential) object detected within a predefined distance threshold.
2. Once a (potential) object is detected, the corresponding frame from the camera is analyzed by the YOLO model to identify the class of the object.
3. If the object is classified as a yellow buoy, the control algorithm commands a lateral deviation maneuver to avoid it.
4. If the object is classified as a horizontal or vertical orange buoy, it is treated as a boundary reference, helping the vehicle maintain its correct path within the course.

This dualsensor setup ensures that both geometric and semantic understanding are achieved while keeping computational demands minimal. The model runs efficiently on lightweight hardware, which in turn supports the system’s energy-efficient design.

3. Results and Discussion

The implemented system successfully identified and avoided buoys in real-time during testing. During offline validation, the YOLO-based model consistently achieved high detection precision across all three buoy classes. When integrated with the LIDAR, the perception pipeline operated with low latency and high reliability.

A valuable observation from the experiments was the effectiveness of a synthetic dataset in training the model. Despite being predominantly AI-generated, the dataset provided sufficiently good and variable enough for robust detection in real-world scenarios. Potentially, this shows a new method for creators of small-scale AI projects to quickly obtain a dataset that is suitable for their purposes without having access to large numbers of photos.

The combination of LIDAR and camera vision systems contributed to better obstacle avoidance, as the LIDAR provided early range-based alerts and the vision module classified objects with contextual understanding.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

This article presents an integrated AI and LIDAR-based obstacle detection system designed for an autonomous surface vehicle competing in TEKNOFEST Aerospace and Technology Festival 2025. The use of synthetic data enabled efficient model training without costly field data collection, while the combination of LIDAR and visual classification ensured robust performance.

The project shows that in small-scale projects, an accurate enough AI object detection and classification model can be trained with little or no access to real photos, using synthetic image generation of a more powerful image generation model. Future work might include incorporating renewable energy sources, such as solar power for onboard systems, and extending the perception framework with depth cameras or multi-sensor system to improve obstacle tracking accuracy. The methodology used here can serve as a foundation for further research into more environmentally friendly autonomous marine technologies.

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